

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ANAGLO-MAWUNEGBLOE****FIRST NAME: CHRIS KWASI****PROGRAM CODE : DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following documents is not a component of dissertation research prepared by students conducting dissertation research?

- Dissertation concept paper.
- Dissertation prospectus.
- The Personal Reflection or Journal of the student's research journey.¹**
- Dissertation manuscript.

2. The dissertation concept paper includes the following sections except:

- Theoretical Analysis of the research topic.²**
- Introduction (What will be included in the paper by the headings indicated as follows).

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

² *Ibid.*, 2.

- Statement of the Problem.
 - Research Questions.
3. **A dissertation concept paper (sometimes referred to as a pre-prospectus paper), which is a brief twelve-to-fifteen-page research proposal, describes the following.**
- What might be studied in the proposed dissertation.
 - Why it needs to be studied.
 - How long it will take to study it.**³
 - How it might be studied.
4. **Which of the following should not be relevant to the researcher when considering the goals of both theoretical (either to contribute new knowledge or extend current theory to a new area) and applied (to use knowledge to contribute directly to the understanding of a problem or generate a solution for the problem) research?**
- Is my worldview aligned with a qualitative research approach, and also, does my intended research problem “fit” with qualitative research?
 - Does my intended research problem “fit” with quantitative research?**⁴
 - Do the problem, the purpose of the study, and the research questions have the potential to serve the goal of the research, either applied or theoretical?
 - Is there sufficient theory to explain the phenomenon, or a reasonable solution to the research problem, sometimes referred to as the “so what?” test?
5. **While reading about researching a topic, it is important that you do not follow this particular question.**
- What do I already know about the topic, and also what do I need to read and know to write the essay?

³ Ibid.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 240.

- How can I copy this material directly into my work?**⁵
- Is this material useful to my topic/argument?
- Can I use this material to support my answer?

6. What are the components of an excellent literature review?

- Excessive information on a particular topic gathered from Wikipedia is credible enough for an excellent literature review.
- A literature review documents a detailed review of past research. It summarises known facts to determine what is unknown concerning the research topic and arguments in the literature and provides study rationale.**⁶
- This critical activity allows for a brief understanding of the research activity and the projected input of the study.
- It is a paraphrase compilation of all recognised published work related to the study.

7. How best can you summarise the whole research in a written article of about 500 words?

- The abstract gives initial impressions of a research article, accurate and meticulously drafted, with detailed findings and conclusions.
- Abstracts are generally within a defined word count. The abstract summarises the study, including the problem statement, purpose, scope, data sources, methodology, essential findings, and inference.**⁷
- An abstract is a very brief portion of an article that includes speciality jargon that may be difficult to read and even harder to understand.
- The abstract should detail your entire project and be written before the rest of the paper.

8. Using the Turabian Author-Date citation style, how do you reference a single-authored book?

⁵ Ibid., 46.

⁶ Ibid., 70–80.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 1110–1115.

- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (parentheses), Title (quotation mark), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
- Author's first name _author's last name. Edition. Date. Title
- (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if existing). Date. Title (italics). Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if existing). Place: Publication Press.**⁸

9. The solution to avoiding Plagiarism is to:

- Direct Copying Without Attribution: Using someone else's words, sentences, or entire paragraphs exactly as they are without quotation marks or giving credit to the original author.
- Paraphrasing Without Acknowledgment: Rephrasing someone else's ideas or work without proper attribution, even if the words are changed, but the original idea or structure remains intact.
- Properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using.**⁹
- Using Another's Work as Your Own: Submitting someone else's work, such as essays, research, or projects, as if you created it, whether purchased, downloaded, or borrowed from a friend or online source, without acknowledgment.

10. The following are correct about full stop except.

- A full stop marks the end of a sentence.
- All footnotes end with a full stop, except those consisting solely of an internet or email address.

⁸ Ibid., 45, 136.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 38.

All footnotes end with a full stop, including those consisting solely of an internet or email address.¹⁰

Do not use a full stop at the end of a heading.

11. Which of these is not correct about question mark?

Every question which expects a separate answer should be followed by a question mark.

The next word after a question mark should begin with a capital letter.

An indirect question.¹¹

There should be no space between the question mark and the preceding word, letter or number.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union. European Commission, 2011.

¹⁰ *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union* (European Commission, 2011), 9.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 15.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.